

AGRO-TOURISM IN FRANCE

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Annotation This article describes in detail the stages of development of agritourism in France, agricultural tourism, production values of agricultural services in France and recommendations for the development of tourism.

Key words: Agricultural tourism, urbanization, production, stressful, French farms, regional and national, breakfast.

Introduction:

Agricultural tourism is a new direction that began its development in Western Europe in the 1960s and 1970s in order to stop mass urbanization. Due to the strong weakening of the connection between nature and the ordinary urban inhabitant, agricultural tourism became widespread, especially in industrially developed countries, where urbanization exceeded the natural resource. Rural tourism as a kind of tourism industry came to us from Europe. Agricultural tourism has been particularly developed in such countries as France, Italy, Germany and England. Its first mention dates back to the beginning of the XIXth century. The 4 main models

of tourism were named: British, French, Italian, and German in honour of these "pioneer" countries (figure 1).

French market:

French tourists are increasingly looking to go green during their holidays to escape a stressful daily life while recharging their batteries in vast natural spaces. They are also looking for authentic stays during which they have the opportunity to interact with locals and learn new things. Agro tourism meets all these expectations and is suitable for adults and children alike. Rural areas thus benefit from substantial economic benefits and this type of tourism helps to increase tourist attendance in these areas.

Although rural tourism has existed in France since the 1970s, the enthusiasm of city dwellers for the countryside has skyrocketed over the past twenty years. As such, agro tourism has jumped from 1% of all tourism in 1995 to 10% in 2019.

In 2016, rural tourism accounted for 30% of overnight stays, i.e. a third of French tourist attendance, according to the General Directorate of Enterprises. Agro tourism, a branch of rural tourism, is defined as a form of tourism whose object is the discovery of the agricultural know-how of a territory and by extension of the landscapes, social practices and culinary specialties resulting from the Agriculture. Today, nearly 14,000 French farms carry out activities related to tourism such as complete stay offers, catering or leisure activities allowing you to discover the life of farmers.

Production value of agricultural services in France between 2014 and 2022 (in billion euros)

Source: statista.com

This statistic shows the production value of agricultural services in France between 2014 and 2022. Agricultural services in France reached an approximate value of 5.6 billion euros in 2022, compared to a production value of 4.5 billion euros in 2014.

Governance:

The French Chambers of Agriculture are self-governing public bodies, managed by elected farmers. Their role is on the one hand to represent the farmers to local, regional and national authorities and on the other hand to offer a broad range of services to farmers and other rural stakeholders. The Chambers' elections are organized every 6 years and the last elections took place between January and March 2013. The French Chambers of Agriculture work as a decentralized network comprising 86 Chambers of Agriculture at district level ("département"), 13 regional Chambers of Agriculture and the national umbrella organization APCA. The Chambers have 4 200 elected members and about 8 000 permanent staff, including about 1300 advisers in the livestock production. The Chambers of Agriculture are involved in nearly all agricultural sectors: plant and animal production; agricultural economics; farm management and strategy; farm tourism and local food products (production, processing and marketing); rural development

and local planning; environment and management of natural resources; agricultural and rural policies. In these various sectors, their activities include information, advice, training, experimentation and demonstration, supporting groups of farmers (~1800 permanent groups), follow-up of “reference farms” (~3 000 including ~2 000 livestock farms), expertise and studies, project co-ordination, and communication. Concerning research and development, the Chambers manage or are involved in about 50 experimental stations, including 10 stations on bovine production, and they implement numerous on-farm trials and demonstrations in connection with farmers’ groups. Furthermore, they are involved in several national R&D networks (“RMT” and “GIS”), especially the thematic network RMT “Prairies demain” (ie. “Grasslands tomorrow”). The APCA employs about 175 staff. It plays a role of expertise, representation, communication and network coordination at national and European level. It also manages various common services for all French Chambers of Agriculture: a training centre for agricultural advisers (“Resolia”), information systems including databases and decision support tools for farmers and advisers (SIRCA), national communication campaigns like INNOV’ACTION (demonstration farms), a web-based platform dedicated to agritourism and local products (“Bienvenue à la Ferme”

Four Regional Chambers of Agriculture (CRA) will be involved in the thematic network “Inno4Grass”:

1- Chamber of Agriculture of Vosges The Chamber of Agriculture of Vosges: Most of the regional coverage of grassland and breeding farms are located in the area of the Vosges, so most of the actions will be done in this area.

Grasslands represent 70% of the farmland in this area, so advisers and technicians of Chamber of Agriculture of Vosges are highly specialized in breeding, grassland and forage production, and that is why most of the actions will be carry out directly by experts employed by the Chamber of Agriculture of Vosges.

2- Regional Chamber of Agriculture of Centre-Val de Loire

The regional Chamber of Agriculture of Centre-Val de Loire employs 20 experts in agronomy, environment, biodiversity, organic production, breeding..., and coordinates six district Chambers of Agriculture, which employ around 400 staff (including 250 farm advisers specialized in agronomy and livestock production). More than 50% of the farmers in Centre region are involved in “agricultural development groups” supported by the Chambers of Agriculture.

3- Regional Chamber of Agriculture of Normandy (CRAN)

The CRAN employs 52 people, including five people in the livestock department. It coordinates 5 district chambers of agriculture, by leading thematic networks, pooling of resources and competencies to provide an efficient local service, well-adapted to the needs of sustainable agriculture. The CRAN and the 5 district chambers are the main contributors to participate in two key organizations, which are:

The Normandy ruminant livestock research centre “POLE RUMINANT” “POLE RUMINANT” was created in 2013 and is led by CRAN. The aim of this centre is to strengthen resources and to organize research actions of on ruminant breeding in Normandy. It associates the chambers of agriculture, INRA, Institut de l’Elevage, ARVALIS Institut du Végétal, livestock consultancy organisms, cattle health organisms, genetic selection organisms, agricultural colleges, AGRIAL (the biggest agricultural cooperative in Normandy: 1.35 billion litres milk collected a year) and the two regional interprofessional centres for Dairy Economy.

The experimental dairy farm “LA BLANCHE MAISON” LA BLANCHE MAISON is an experimental dairy farm. It has numerous partners: the Normandy Chambers of Agriculture, the French livestock Institute (Institut de l’Elevage), the French national institute for agricultural research (INRA), the French Institute for vegetal research (ARVALIS Institut du Végétal), a livestock consultancy organism and an agricultural college. The work consists in experimenting new livestock systems, including the assessment of environmental criteria. The farm owns 70 hectares of agricultural land, including 60 hectares of

grass, and 70 cows of “Normande” cattle breed. Since 2011, the experiments’ goals are to assess and compare two high economic and environmental performance dairy systems with objectives of productivity, efficiency and autonomy (maximum reduction of inputs). One of these two systems is based on grass – feeding, the other includes corn silage. The experimental dairy farm has a specific and high level experience to manage innovation in grass-based production systems.

4-Regional Chamber of Agriculture of Pays de la Loire
The network of Chambers of Agriculture of Pays de la Loire consists of one regional and five departmental Chambers of agriculture. It employs experts in large domains of agriculture (e.g. agronomy, forage production, breeding, organic farming, environment) in order to provide advices and references to farmers. In collaboration with IDELE (French livestock institute), it follows up networks of livestock farms (dairy and beef cattle, sheep). The main goal of our applied research is to improve the competitiveness of the livestock farms.

Agritourism networks: There are two major organizations in France qualifying this type of stay, Accueil Paysan and Bienvenue à la Ferme. The first is a network that was created in 1987 and which today has 900 members in France as well as 300 others in 32 different countries. Accueil Paysan is made up of farmers and rural actors committed to peasant agriculture as well as sustainable, fair and united tourism. The tourist services offered by this federation are numerous and varied, such as peasant lodges, peasant campsites, guest rooms on the farm, reception tables and many more.

There are many clever places to visit and things to watch. Nice cottages, beautiful countryside and marvelous nature. You can even experience gardening and farming, picking up vegetables and looking at how it all works. Many French tourist farms are well-equipped, having modern features, such as high garden beds mixing it with traditional approach.

The second network, Bienvenue à la Ferme, was created in 1988 and currently has nearly 1,000 national members, making it the number one network in terms of

number of members. In addition to the different types of accommodation on the farm promoted by the network, a large number of activities are also offered to visitors such as visits to educational farms, introduction to horse riding... Welcome to the Farm also allows everyone these member farmers to make direct sales of the products resulting from their production. The turnover from the many activities offered by the members of the network amounted to 1 billion euros in 2016.

In addition, for the 4th consecutive year, Bienvenue à la Ferme is joining forces with to launch their joint call for projects called “Tous à la Ferme”. Two new partners have been added to the program this year, Les Grappes, which is a platform for direct purchases and reservations with winegrowers, and Winalist, a digital platform for booking wine tourism activities.

Agro tourism - Sustainable way of travelling in France

France is not only the world’s most visited country; it’s also the first agricultural producer in Europe. However, French farmers are provided with low income; agricultural productions rely heavily on the unpredictable weather and farmers are more and more indebted to pay back loans contracted to face the rise of lands’ prices.

Consequently, farmers often need to reconsider their livelihoods and search for additional and safer sources of revenue. Agritourism is one of those alternatives, offering immersive and unique sustainable experiences to tourists. This also allows farmers to gain more revenue, preserve their lifestyle, and connect with people from around the world. Associations like Accueil Paysan or Bienvenue à la Ferme were created in order to create collectives for farmers and agricultural stakeholders to support traditional farming lifestyle and to promote a more sustainable and fair tourism as a financial lifeline. They support French farms wishing to diversify their activity beyond agricultural production, and assist farmers in the organization of tours and in the creation of table d’hôtes and guestrooms to welcome tourists.

Through farm stays, by purchasing local products or by taking part in agro tourism activities, you contribute to improving farmers' lives with additional financial resources.

Beside agro tourism activities, farmers organized educational tours for special-need and vulnerable communities. Disabled or aging people can benefit from pedagogic visits through the farms and with the animals, whereas farmers seize the opportunity of young children touring to orient them to a more sustainable lifestyle. Other groups of people which are generally left out get involved in farming projects as well; women victims of abuse, young people who dropped out of school or were heavily bullied, former prisoners trying to reintegrate in society, and vulnerable families.

With agro tourism in France, you contribute to supporting rural farmers, who are then able to create opportunities for those in need. Your impact goes further than to your host directly; you contribute to local development and to helping vulnerable communities.

Food is so important to French people that the 'Gastronomic meal of the French' has even been inscribed by UNESCO on the Representative List of the Intangible Cultural Heritage of Humanity. Eating is a special moment for French people, who consider each meal a celebration, and a moment spent together around qualitative products.

Agro tourism in France offers you the possibility to stay with farmers who grow and cook their own meals. You can't find any fresher meal than the one prepared with products cultivated by the people serving you. With no intermediary, food goes straight from the field to your plate, you discover a new kind of authentic French delicacy. This is true farm-to-table luxury. Farmer hosts take care of you and of your stomach from breakfast to dinner, focusing on the quality and the sustainability of each ingredient.

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